

Pathways Toward Universal Electricity Access in Kenya

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Keywords

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Executive Summary

Kenya, like many other Sub-Saharan Africa countries, has set high targets to ensure universal access to electricity by 2030. This study sought to identify a least-cost path to universal electricity access in Kenya by 2030. It examined least cost scenarios that combine and exclude the use of stand-alone solar photovoltaic systems, and determined the total investment, generation capacity, and combination of technologies that contribute to the least cost. Results indicate that including stand-alone solar photovoltaic systems as a technology option would cost the country roughly four times less than excluding the technology. In addition, excluding the stand-alone solar photovoltaic systems results in approximately four times the generation capacity requirements. Kenya's current national electrification strategy prioritises grid extension and intensification. The results of the study suggest that grid extension and intensification are not the least cost options, hence, priority should be shifted to stand-alone solar photovoltaic systems. This can partly be achieved by increasing the annual subsidies on stand-alone solar photovoltaic systems.

1. Introduction

In Sub-Saharan Africa, roughly 50% of the population lacks access to electricity. As many emerging and developing countries consider electrification vital for economic development, there is a need to increase electricity access in the region. Kenya has emerged as one of the countries with the fastest electrification rates (76%) (IEA, IRENA, UNSD, World Bank, WHO, 2023) in the region aiming to achieve 100% electrification by 2030. With the increased rate of electrification, the country requires a least-cost strategy targeting remote and underserved regions while leveraging its renewable energy potential. This study set out to investigate a least-cost path to universal electricity access

in Kenya by 2030. It considered the effects of including stand-alone (SA) solar photovoltaic (PV) systems to answer the following research questions:

- What combination of technologies can provide 100% electrification with the least investment costs?
- What is the total investment required to achieve 100% electrification by 2030?
- What is the total installed generation capacity required to achieve 100% electrification by 2030?
- How do stand-alone solar PV technologies affect the investments required for 100% electrification?

2. Methodology

Two electrification scenarios were developed on the Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET), a Geographical Information System (GIS)-based LCOE optimization program. The two scenarios included Scenario 1- electrification including the use of SA PV as a technology option, and Scenario 2- electrification excluding the use of stand-alone solar PV as a technology option. This study focused on electrification at the household level. The assumptions for the study include an urban tier target of 2,117 kWh and a rural tier target of 803 kWh, without forced intensification of the grid. In addition, there was no cap on the number of new connections or the amount of generation capacity that can be added to the grid.

Technology options considered in the OnSSET model are the existing grid, grid expansion, stand-alone solar PV, PV hybrid mini-grid, wind mini-grid, and hydro mini-grid.

Data used in the study included information obtained from, Kenya Power (2024), GADM (2023), 'Kenya wind speed' (2023), Global Solar Atlas (2019), Elvidge *et al.* (2023), The Malaria Atlas project (2015), and Khavari *et al.* (2020). The variables used for model scenarios are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Variables used for model scenarios

Variable	Value
Start year	2020
End year	2030
End-year electrification rate target	100%
Intermediate target year	2025
Intermediate electrification rate target	89.50%
Urban target tier	4
Rural target tier	3
Buffer distance (km) for automatic intensification	0
Discount rate	11.50%
Population in 2020	47,564,296

Variable	Value
Population in 2030	57,811,161
Urban population ratio in 2020	28%
Urban population ratio in 2030	30%
Number of people per urban household	3
Number of people per rural household	4.3
Electrification rate in 2020	71.50%
Urban electrification rate in 2020	94.10%
Rural electrification rate in 2020	62.7%
Grid generation cost (USD/kWh)	0.083
Grid power plants capital cost (USD/kWh)	1,500
Grid losses	23%
Ratio of base grid demand to peak demand	80%
The additional cost per round of electrification	10%
Diesel price (USD/litre)	1.41
Mini-grid Hydro capital cost (USD/kW)	2,500
SA PV capital cost (USD/kW) for systems under 20 W	1,937
SA PV capital cost (USD/kW) for systems between 21-50 W	1,860
SA PV capital cost (USD/kW) for systems between 51-100 W	1,713
SA PV capital cost (USD/kW) for systems between 101-200 W	1,372
SA PV capital cost (USD/kW) f for systems over 200 W	1,162
Cost of MV lines in USD/km	19,605
Cost of LV lines in USD/km	8,000
Capacity of MV lines in kV/line	33
Capacity of LV lines in kV/line	0.24
Maximum length of LV lines (km)	0.5
Cost of HV lines in USD/km	160,000
Maximum distance grid extension using MV lines (km)	50
Cap on annual new grid connections	Null
Cap on annual new grid generation capacity (MW)	Null

3. Results

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of technologies with the lowest LCOE in different areas of Kenya. The results indicate that including SA PV systems as a technology option resulted in investment costs four times lower than excluding the technology. When SA PV was included in the model, four technology options were mapped by OnSSET as least cost: existing grid, SA PV, PV mini-grid, and wind mini-grid.

Figure 1: Least cost scenario, with SA PV

When SA PV systems were excluded from the model, technology options mapped as least cost were the existing grid, grid extension, PV mini-grid, wind mini-grid, and hydro mini-grid. A comparison of the distribution of technologies in the two scenarios is shown in Figure 2.

Scenario comparison

Figure 2: Maps comparing the distribution of least-cost technologies

Scenario 2 (without SA PV) resulted in an investment of 11,070 million USD for a capacity of 15,365MW while scenario 1 had an investment of 3,800 million USD for a capacity of 3,054MW. Figure 3 provides a breakdown of the investments for each technology option

Figure 3: Investments per scenario (million USD)

According to Figure 3, without SA PV, PV mini-grid takes up approximately 83% of total investments. Conversely, SA PV takes up the largest share of total investments in scenario 1 (74%). Similar to the share of investments, the two technologies, PV mini-grid in scenario 2 and SA PV in scenario 1 take up the largest share of required generation capacity and new connections as depicted in Table 2.

Table 2: Total generation capacity and new connections for 100% electrification

	With SA PV	Without SA PV
New connections		
Existing grid	1,956,551	1,956,551
Grid extension	0	1,055,961
SA PV	5,381,720	0
PV Hybrid mini-grid	333	4,278,964
Wind mini-grid	1,755	29,646
Hydro mini-grid	0	33,116
Total	7,340,359	7,354,238
Generation capacity		
Existing grid	609.02	609.02
Grid extension	0.00	157.14
SA PV	2,435.84	0.00
PV Hybrid mini-grid	1.33	14,572.46
Wind mini-grid	8.74	19.01
Hydro mini-grid	0.00	7.52
Total	3,054.94	15,365.15

4. Discussion

In 2018, Kenya launched the Kenya National Electrification Strategy (KNES) as a roadmap to universal electricity access by 2022. The implementation of the strategy was expected to reduce poverty, create more employment opportunities, and contribute to an increase in industrial development in Kenya. In addition, the strategy was expected to accelerate economic growth by 10% each year. KNES prioritises grid expansion and grid intensification technology options, with SA PV expected to account for 18% of new connections (Ministry of Energy, 2018). From the current study, the least cost option has SA PV accounting for roughly 70% of new connections. In addition, the total investments required for scenario 1 are significantly lower than the scenario excluding SA PV. This difference may be explained by falling energy technology costs—especially related to solar panels and batteries. Since KNES considers grid expansion and intensification within 15 km of the existing grid, it also limits the use of alternative technologies within these regions. The current study considers all technologies and maps based on the least levelized cost of electricity to each settlement area. The results indicate that SA PV will be the least cost option to target the majority of unelectrified households in Kenya.

Kenya Vision 2030 recognises electricity as a basic need and an important component of every household. Currently, approximately 90% of electricity generation in Kenya is from renewable or clean energy sources (IEA, 2021). According to the International Renewable Energy Agency, (2022), newly commissioned renewable capacity in 2022 had lower costs compared to fossil fuel-fired electricity. Moreover, the cost-competitive role of renewables is expected to help tackle the energy and climate crises. However, the retail price for electricity in Kenya has maintained an increasing trend since 2017 (Cowling, 2023) despite renewables accounting for a larger share of the energy mix. In line with the Kenya National Electrification Strategy, increasing access to electricity to promote economic growth and development requires electricity to be affordable. If the strategy continues to prioritise grid expansion and intensification, households will have no option but to rely on expensive grid electricity, limiting the productive use of energy. This study proposes subsidies, incentives, and programs that ensure households have access to affordable electricity.

The accuracy of the results is subject to the quality of the data used and the assumptions made for the scenarios. Future work can explore interventions to maximize the use of stand-alone solar PV systems as part of the national electrification strategy.

5. Conclusion

As Kenya strives to achieve 100% electrification, the country requires a least-cost strategy to target remote and underserved regions. This study explored two scenarios, with and without stand-alone solar PV systems, based on levelized cost of electricity optimization. The study found that the scenario with stand-alone solar PV required the least investment and combined technologies such as existing grid, wind mini-grid, and PV mini-grid. These results suggest that the current national electrification strategy that prioritises grid extension and intensification may result in higher investment to achieve 100% electrification by 2030. Interventions such as subsidies and incentives can be increased to encourage the adoption of stand-alone solar PV systems to reduce the total investments required for universal electricity access.

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Appendices

GIS data sources

Data	GIS type	Source
Administrative boundaries	Polygon	(GADM, 2023)
Medium-voltage and high-voltage lines	Lines	(Kenya Power, 2024)
Existing service transformers	Points	(Kenya Power, 2024)
Substations	Points	(Kenya Power, 2024)
Road network	Lines	Energy data
Settlement delineation (clusters)	Polygons	(Khavari <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Population distribution	Raster	(Kenya Power, 2024)
Global Horizontal Irradiation	Raster	(Global Solar Atlas, 2019)
Small-scale hydropower sites	Points	(Kenya Power, 2024)
Wind velocity (m/s)	Raster	('Kenya wind speed', no date)
Travel hours (min or h)	Raster	(The Malaria Atlas Project, 2015)
Night-time lights	Raster	(Elvidge <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
Existing mini-grid locations	Points	(Kenya Power, 2024)